

Noise Pollution and Human Health: An Emerging Threat to the Right to Health

Sachin Kumar¹ & Vivek Singh²

1. Research Scholar, Faculty of Legal Studies, Motherhood University, Roorkee, Uttarakhand
2. Associate Professor, Faculty of Legal Studies, Motherhood University, Roorkee, Uttarakhand

Received : 24/01/2026 1st BPR : 09/02/2026 2nd BPR : 27/02/2026 Accepted : 14/03/2026

Abstract

Health is a fundamental requirement for a pleasant and dignified human life. Due to the importance of health, it has been considered a form of wealth. In a welfare state, the state has the obligation to give importance to and protect the people's right to health and to mitigate all factors that violate the right to health. Under the right to health, every person has the right, without any discrimination, to have their health protected from all factors that affect their health; and every human being has the right to attain the highest attainable standard of health. The concept of the right to health is linked to the holistic nature of health; it encompasses being healthy, maintaining health, easy and equal approach to healthcare services, and protection from various factors that affect health. Since the emergence of human rights, the right to health has been given importance in all human rights instruments. The Indian Constitution does not explicitly enshrine the right to health as a fundamental right, but the Indian judiciary has recognized it as a fundamental right by considering it an important component of the right to life. Any form of environmental pollution directly affects human life and health. Noise pollution, a silent, overlooked, yet significant environmental issue, affects human health, causing various physical and mental diseases. Regarding noise pollution, the common perception is that it is only related to the loss of human hearing capacity and is therefore overlooked as a serious health hazard. Noise pollution, by affecting human health, causes many serious and incurable diseases that endanger human life. This research paper examines the meaning, necessity, and importance of the right to health and assesses the various diseases caused by noise pollution that violate the right to health.

Key words: Welfare State, Health, Constitution, Environmental Pollution, Noise, Health Hazards.

Introduction:-

Health is one of the various primary needs of a happy and dignified human life. Only a healthy person can live a successful, happy and purposeful life. Keeping in view the importance of health, it has been termed as wealth and it is said that a healthy person has innumerable dreams and goals but a sick person has only one dream and that is to get well soon. Health includes both physical and mental health. A healthy mind resides within a healthy body. In the enumeration of various pleasures, health is considered the first pleasure. The right to health is directly related to the right to life. The right to life, which is the root of all rights and is supreme among all other rights, means a dignified life. Health is also one of the various essential elements that make human life dignified. The right to health is a human right which is equally available to all without any discrimination. Any situation that deteriorates health is a direct challenge to this human right. There are many factors which directly affect health, such as income, social status, education, work place environment, social relations, natural disasters, diet, lifestyle, genetics and environmental conditions. Environmental conditions affect human life and human health (physical and mental). Environmental degradation in the form of pollution has adverse effects on human health. It is futile to imagine human life being pleasant and dignified in a polluted environment. Different types of environmental pollution affect human health and human life in different ways. Noise pollution, which is a type of environmental pollution, is generally not taken

seriously but it is true that noise pollution causes serious adverse effects on human health (physical and mental). Research studies show that noise pollution acts as a silent killer. By affecting health, it not only poses a challenge to the human right to health but also violates the most important human right, the right to life. In the present times, due to various activities, environmental pollution, which also includes noise pollution, has taken a terrible form and its adverse effects on human health have also increased in the same proportion.

Concept of the Right to Health:-

According to the principles mentioned in the Constitution of the World Health Organization¹, "Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity". The right to health is an important human right directly related to the dignity and existence of human life. A happy and dignified life is not possible in the absence of good health. Bad health is a sign of unhappiness and misery, while a person with good health is happy and leads his life towards prosperity. "The enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health is one of the fundamental rights of every human being without distinction of race, religion, political-belief, economic or social condition"². There is a deep and direct relationship between health and life. The existence of life completely depends on health. The right to health is generally seen in a narrow form, and it is concluded that only the provision of health services and treatment comes under the right to health, but it is worth noting that just as the right to life is a broad concept, similarly the right to health is also a right with a broad meaning. The right to health includes the right to medical treatment, availability of health services as well as protection from all those external factors which directly or indirectly affect health. The right to health is not merely a single right, but a multifaceted one encompassing many rights. These include the right to timely access to appropriate healthcare services, access to adequate sanitation, healthy food and sufficient nutrition, ensuring a healthy environment, protection of health from environmental pollution, maternal care and services, elimination of discrimination in healthcare services, access to health education, and more.

Status of the Right to Health in a Welfare State:-

Before the concept of State, human life was solitary. There was a complete lack of mutual respect and a sense of collective responsibility and a state of liberty without any responsibility prevailed. This state of human life was called the natural state. "This period was called the Golden Age by John Locke, in which there was a lack of security of property"³. In this situation the feeling of self-security was strong. In order to get out of the state of mutual conflict and feeling of insecurity, society was brought into existence by man for the purpose of protection of life and property and to subject himself to the obedience of an authority. The State emerged as a political unit which could provide security to the people under its control and the systems created by it were to be followed by all those people. The State was a unit equipped with rights, powers and responsibilities.

Over time, the concept of the State began its journey of development from its original form. With the increasing dependence on the State, its responsibilities also changed. The State now became the focal point for fulfilling other expectations and needs besides the sole purpose of merely providing security. It was the responsibility of the State to give priority to the collective welfare of the citizens under its jurisdiction and from here the concept of 'welfare state' based on the spirit of public welfare emerged. The concept of 'welfare state' means a system of governance in which the State discharges its responsibilities in the spirit of collectivism, equality, welfare of all and especially the welfare of the people of the marginalized class. "The term 'welfare state' refers to a type of political system in which a government plays a key role in the protection and promotion of the economic and social well-being of its citizens"⁴.

With time, the functions and responsibilities of the welfare state have also increased. Initially, its responsibilities were limited to maintenance of law and order, protection from external attacks and to provide justice. Now, these responsibilities also include protection of human rights, poverty alleviation, availability of nutritious food, social reforms, health improvement, agricultural development, employment, social security, environmental protection and other expedient services. Health improvement and health protection are one of the responsibilities and objectives of a welfare

state. It is the responsibility of a welfare state to make effective policies for health protection, health improvement and healthy life to all its citizens.

All the essential elements of a welfare state are included in the Indian Constitution. The provisions of the Preamble and Part IV of the Indian Constitution declare India as a welfare state. "The aim of Constitution makers was to establish a welfare state in India. The ideals towards which the Constitution aims are clearly mentioned in the Directive Principles of State Policy and the dream of establishing a welfare state can be realised only by working in accordance with those principles"⁵. The Preamble of the Indian Constitution indicates the goals for which the Constitution is made. "The Preamble is the key to knowing the thoughts of the Constitution makers"⁶; and is "a part of the Constitution"⁷. In the preamble of the Indian Constitution, providing social, economic and political justice to the Indian people is one of the main objectives of the Constitution. The idea of establishing a welfare state in India is seen in the Preamble. Part IV of the Indian Constitution mentions the Directive Principles of State Policy, which contain the objectives whose observance and achievement is the responsibility of the State. The ideal situation of establishing a welfare and socialist society as envisaged in the Preamble of the Constitution can be achieved only when the government tries to implement the Directive Principles of State Policy, According to Dr. Ambedkar, "the goal of a welfare state is inherent in the Directive Principles of State Policy"⁸.

The Right to Health in International Human Rights Instruments:-

The right to health has been given a prominent place in all major international instruments related to human rights. Article 25 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948⁹, stipulates that "Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services..."; Article 12, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, 1966¹⁰, makes the following provisions regarding the right of all individuals to physical and mental health: "(1) The States Parties to the present Covenant recognize the right of everyone to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health. (2) The steps to be taken by the States Parties to the present Covenant to achieve the full realization of this right shall include those necessary for-.... , (b) The improvement of all aspects of environmental and industrial hygiene"; Article 24(1) of the International Convention, the Convention on the Rights of the Child¹¹, which contains provisions relating to the rights of the child, enshrines the right to health for child in the following way: "States Parties recognize the right of the child to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health and to facilities for the treatment of illness and rehabilitation of health. States Parties shall strive to ensure that no child is deprived of his or her right of access to such health care services".

Article 16(1), African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, 1981¹², provides that, "Every individual shall have the right to enjoy the best attainable state of physical and mental health". Regarding the availability of the right to health for persons with disabilities, Article 25 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2006¹³, includes the following provision: "States Parties recognize that persons with disabilities have the right to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health without discrimination on the basis of disability". Article 11, European Social Charter, 1961¹⁴; stipulates that: "With a view to ensuring the effective exercise of the right to protection of health, the Contracting parties undertake, either directly or in co-operation with public or private organizations, to take appropriate measures designed inter-alia: to remove as far as possible the causes of ill-health".

Thus, we find that the right to health has been given a prominent place and importance in all the important instruments that protect, promote, and guarantee human rights. It is a right of every individual, granted equally to all without discrimination, and the responsibility for its protection and respect rests with the State.

Right to Health under Indian Constitution:-

The right to health is not explicitly and specifically mentioned as a fundamental right in the Indian Constitution. However, in this regard, Part IV of the Constitution, under the Directive Principles of State Policy, imposes a duty on the State to formulate its policies with the objective of creating a social order for the promotion of the welfare of the people. Article 38(1) stipulates, "The State shall strive to promote the welfare of the people by securing and protecting as effectively as it may a social order in which

justice, social, economic and political, shall inform all the institutions of the national life". The Constitution imposes a clear obligation on the State with regard to health protection. Article 39 (e) makes the following provision in this regard- "The State shall, in particular, direct its policy towards securing- (e) that the health and strength of workers, men and women, and the tender age of children are not abused and that citizens are not forced by economic necessity to enter vocations unsuited to their age or strength". The Constitution, in Article 47, imposes the following responsibility on the State regarding the improvement and promotion of public health: "The State shall regard the raising of the level of nutrition and the standard of living of its people and the improvement of public health as among its primary duties and, in particular, the State shall endeavor to bring about prohibition of the consumption except for medicinal purposes of intoxicating drinks and of drugs which are injurious to health".

The credit for establishing the right to health as a fundamental right under the Indian Constitution goes to the judiciary. The Indian judiciary, through its broad interpretation of Article 21, which guarantees the right to life, has included various rights that are not explicitly mentioned in the Constitution but are essential for making the right to life comprehensive. The judiciary has expanded the right to life to encompass a life of dignity and has recognized various rights that contribute to a dignified human life as fundamental rights.

In various landmark judgments, the judiciary has recognized the right to health as an integral part of the right to life, thereby granting it the status of a fundamental right. In *Unnikrishnan, J.P. v. State of Andhra Pradesh*,¹⁵ it was held, "the maintenance and improvement of public health is the duty of the State to fulfill its Constitutional obligations cast on it under Article 21 of the Constitution". In *Consumer Education and Research Centre v. Union of India*,¹⁶ the Supreme Court explicitly held, "the right to health and medical care is a fundamental right under Article 21 of the Constitution". In *Bandhua Mukti Morcha v. Union of India*,¹⁷ the Apex Court addressed the conditions necessary for enjoyment of health and said, "right to live with human dignity also involves right to protection of health". In *Virender Gaur v. State of Haryana*,¹⁸ the Supreme Court held, "environmental, ecological, air and water pollution etc., should be regarded as amounting to violation of right to health guaranteed by Article 21 of the Constitution". In *CESC Ltd. v. Subhash Chandra Bose*,¹⁹ the Supreme Court held, "Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity". In *Occupational Health and Safety Association v. Union of India and Others*,²⁰ for protection of health of workers, the Supreme Court held, "when workers are engaged in hazardous and risky jobs/occupations, the responsibility and duty, regarding protection of health of workers, on the State becomes double fold". Thus, in the Indian Constitution, the right to health holds a dual status: it is both an obligation on the State and a fundamental right declared by the judiciary. It is an essential part of the right to life and forms the basis of the concept of a dignified and holistic life.

Effects of Noise Pollution on Human Health:-

There has always been a general indifference among the public regarding the harmful effects of noise pollution, which is commonly defined as an excess of undesirable and disturbing sound in our environment. Various research studies show that noise pollution is just as dangerous as other forms of pollution, and based on its harmful effects, it has been labeled a silent killer, "Noise is not only considered as an environmental stressor but it is also labeled as a 'silent killer' due to its enormous health hazards"²¹. The intensity of noise can cause fatal diseases and can also directly lead to death. The adverse effects of noise pollution on human health are sometimes gradual and sometimes immediate, leading to life-threatening diseases and violating a fundamental human right- right to health. "Chronic exposure to noise from transport contributes to 66,000 premature deaths annually in Europe, while also leading to around 50,000 new cardiovascular disease cases and 22,000 cases of type 2 diabetes"²². Noise pollution affects human physical and mental health; it causes various physical illness as well as various mental disorders.

The various physical and mental illness caused by excessive noise can be divided into two categories: auditory and non-auditory effects. Auditory effects include the way noise pollution affects human hearing capacity, while non-auditory effects include other side effects of noise pollution, such as stress, insomnia, anxiety, heart disease, high blood pressure, depression, impact on mental ability,

etc. "The adverse health effects of noise pollution include poor health, impaired learning environments, and non-auditory effects such as hearing loss, sleep disturbances and stress, headaches, irritability, high blood pressure, and reduced concentration"²³.

The adverse effects of noise pollution on human health are as follows:-

(a) Hearing Impairment- Hearing impairment is a common side effect of excessive noise exposure. People who are exposed to loud and prolonged noise often experience a decrease in hearing ability, and in some cases, it can even lead to deafness. Whether it's workers affected by excessive noise at the workplace, individuals affected by road traffic noise, or people living near airports, the impact of noise on hearing ability has been commonly observed in all these groups. "Road traffic noise is associated with various health problems, including hearing impairment"²⁴. "Workers in industries such as manufacturing, construction and mining are particularly vulnerable to hearing damage due to consistent exposure to high noise levels"²⁵. "Occupational noise exposure resulted in evidence of Noise-Induced Hearing Loss (NIHL) in approximately 50% of workers, as detected by pure-tone audiometry; prolonged exposure to noise levels exceeding 85dB led to sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL)"²⁶. "In areas where noise levels were measured up to 106dB, it was found that 93% of the people experienced hearing difficulties, mostly of the sensorineural type, affecting the right ear more often; the highest prevalence of hearing problems was observed in the working age group (36-45 years) and among unskilled laborers, and this was directly co-related with the intensity of the noise"²⁷. The effect of noise pollution on human hearing depends on the amount, intensity, and duration of exposure to the noise.

(b) Stress and Anxiety- Excessive noise and its intensity affect human mental health and increase stress level. Noise accelerates the release of cortisol hormone in the human body, which is responsible for inducing stress. "Chronic exposure to road traffic noise can elevate cortisol levels"²⁸. "Road traffic noise is associated with various health problems, including increased stress levels"²⁹. "Chronic exposure to road traffic noise can lead to hypertension and elevated cortisol levels"³⁰. "Residents with high ambient noise exposure had significantly higher rates of anxiety symptoms"³¹. "Long-term exposure to environmental noise is associated with a significant increase in anxiety symptoms among adults"³². "Epidemiological evidence shows traffic noise raises depression odds by 4-12% and anxiety by 9-12% per 10 dB increases in noise levels, with stronger links for aircraft noise; suicide risks increase with road/rail noise"³³.

(c) Hypertension- The link between noise and hypertension has been proven by various research studies. Prolonged exposure to loud noise increases blood pressure, and persistent excessive noise in one's life establishes hypertension as a chronic condition in the human body. Individuals who regularly endure high levels of noise, such as those exposed to road traffic noise, those working in noisy environments, and those who accept aviation noise as a part of their lives, have been found to have a higher incidence of hypertension compared to people living or working in quieter areas. "Chronic exposure to road traffic noise can lead to hypertension"³⁴. "Prolonged exposure to high levels of urban noise increases the likelihood of elevated systolic/diastolic blood pressure and resistant hypertension in older adults, an association that remains strong even after adjusting for confounding factors"³⁵. "Noise pollution in urban *Thoothukudi* (Tamil Nadu) co-relates with hypertension due to prolonged high-decibel exposure from port and traffic sources"³⁶.

(d) Insomnia and Sleeping Disturbance- Sleep is a vital necessity for human life, and its disruption negatively impacts a person's physical and mental health, behavior, and performance. Noise intensity disrupts the sleep process, making it difficult to fall asleep and causing sleep disturbances. A large portion of the population is affected by sleep disturbances caused by noise pollution. "Almost 4.6 million Europeans suffer from severe sleep disturbances due to noise from transport"³⁷. "Exposure to traffic noise is significantly associated with all three main symptoms of insomnia: difficulty in falling asleep, difficulty in staying asleep, and waking up early in the morning"³⁸. The excessive volume and intensity of noise produced at night significantly affects the sleep process. "Night time urban noise is linked to an increase in mental health problems, such as sleep disturbances that exacerbate symptoms of anxiety and depression; Prolonged exposure to noise contributes to emotional deregulation, with

poor sleep quality acting as a key mediating factor; Statistical co-relations have shown a higher likelihood of psychiatric disorders in noisier environments, highlighting the need for strategies to reduce urban noise³⁹.

(e) Heart Related Problems- Continuous exposure to noise, especially loud noise, increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases. Excessive noise affects the hormonal structure and balance in the human body, constricting arteries and accelerating heart rate. A research highlights that, "chronic exposure to high levels of noise can lead to significant health problems such as hypertension, heart disease, and stroke"⁴⁰. The continuous and prolonged occurrence of these processes negatively impacts heart health. High noise levels are a known cause of high blood pressure, which puts stress on the heart and significantly increases the risk of heart attack, heart failure and stroke. "Residents exposed to noise levels above 60dB(A) were found to have 2.24 times higher odds of having Ischemic Heart Disease (IHD) compared to those in quieter areas"⁴¹. This risk increases as the noise intensity level increases. "Higher traffic noise exposure is significantly associated with higher prevalence of Coronary Artery Disease (CAD); with each 5dB(A) increase in noise level, the odds of CAD increased (e.g., 2.25× higher risk per 5dB(A))"⁴². The risk of cardiovascular diseases has been found to be higher in people who are constantly exposed to road traffic noise and occupational noise. "A major cardiovascular risk factor as commonly reported among traffic policemen exposed to noise levels above 65dB(A)"⁴³. "Road traffic noise is associated with various health problems, including increased risk of cardiovascular diseases"⁴⁴.

(f) Effects on Cognitive Health- Cognitive health refers to the human brain's capacity for learning, thinking, studying, remembering, making decisions, and concentrating. For ease of life and freedom of decision-making, it is crucial that cognitive health be protected from all factors that negatively affect it, one of which is noise pollution. "Noise damages cognitive skills"⁴⁵. The constant presence of high-intensity noise affects the brain's ability to concentrate and weakens memory, with the paramount impact on school children. The intensity of noise makes the learning and comprehension process more difficult. "Adolescents aged 13-15 years exposed to excessive noise showed significantly higher academic stress, delayed attention span, poorer concentration, and reduced verbal and visuospatial working memory compared to adolescents in less noisy areas; noise intensity increases stress and decreases working memory performance"⁴⁶. "Urban noise levels in India exceed the WHO limits, leading to distraction, reduced work efficiency, and cognitive difficulties; prolonged exposure to noise can cause stress on the central nervous system, increasing the risk of cognitive impairment"⁴⁷. "A study highlights the need for comprehensive research into how noise pollution affects mental well-being and cognitive performance, as these effects can have far reaching implications for individuals' quality of life and overall health; and this study indicates that exposure to high levels of environmental noise can impair learning abilities and academic performance"⁴⁸.

(g) Effects on the Health of Pregnant Women- Pregnant women face many health complications due to their pregnancy, and this condition makes them highly susceptible to the adverse effects of noise pollution. Noise pollution not only affects their physical and mental health but also the health of the baby growing in their womb. Due to the complex condition of pregnant women, noise pollution increases the stress-producing hormones in them to a risky level, resulting in increased risk of insomnia, anxiety, high blood pressure and premature delivery. The developing fetus can also suffer from physical and mental health problems, and even disabilities, as a result of noise pollution. "Pregnant women exposed to prolonged high levels of occupational noise were found to have eminent blood pressure, fasting blood glucose, plasma lipids, fetal heart rate, and larger fetal size"⁴⁹. "Exposure to noise levels above 80dB(A) during pregnancy increases the risk of hypertensive disorders and pre-eclampsia, and this risk is higher during the first pregnancy"⁵⁰. "An adverse relationship has been found between noise exposure and fetal weight; with every 6 dB(A) increase in noise intensity reducing fetal weight by an average of 19grams"⁵¹.

(h) Impact on Children's Development- Children due to their tender age, are more sensitive to noise; excessive noise and its intensity can hinder their physical and mental development. Noise pollution significantly harms children's physical growth, hearing ability and cardiovascular health, and also hinders their thinking, and emotional development. Exposure to loud noise for long periods of time

stunts children's physical development, increases their risk of obesity, and also impacts their intellectual development, affecting their ability to speak and learning. "It is estimated that over half a million children in Europe experience reading difficulties and about 63,000 experience behavioral issues due to transport noise; High noise levels are also linked to approximately 2,72,000 cases of overweight children"⁵². The adverse effects of noise pollution have been commonly observed in children living in or attending schools located in noisy areas such as industrial areas, crowded places, and areas near airports. "Aviation noise is linked to adverse health effects, including sleep disturbances, cardiovascular problems and cognitive impairments in children"⁵³.

Conclusion:-

In the concept of a welfare state, all efforts to make human life happy have been given priority by keeping human welfare paramount. Health is a crucial component of the completeness and dignity of human life. Every factor that affects human health ultimately affects human life. Like other pollutions, noise pollution also affects human life and health. The right to health, which holds a significant place as a fundamental human right, is undermined by noise pollution. The right to health is a multifaceted concept; it includes equal access to healthcare services as well as protection from various factors that affect health. The intensity of noise, in a subtle and insidious way, causes various physical and mental illness that threaten the dignity and well-being of human life. The health consequences of noise pollution are long-term, leading to serious consequences over time and manifesting as incurable diseases. Noise pollution disproportionately affects vulnerable groups, as its effects are greater and more immediate due to their heightened sensitivity. As a society, the ill effects of noise pollution need to be taken seriously and measures to control it need to be taken, only then it is possible to guarantee the right to health in a welfare state.

References

- 1 Constitution of the World Health Organization, World Health Organization, available at: <https://www.who.int/about/governance/constitution> (last visited on December 16, 2025)
- 2 *Id.*
- 3 Tripathi, T. P., *Jurisprudence* 98 (4th ed., Allahabad Law Agency, Allahabad, 1998).
- 4 Welfare State, Investopedia, available at: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/w/welfare-state.asp> (last visited on December 16, 2025)
- 5 Pandey, J. N., *The Constitution of India* 38 (Central Law Agency, Allahabad, 50th ed., 2017).
- 6 *In Berubari Union*, AIR 1960 SC 845
- 7 *Keshwanand Bharti v. State of Kerala*, AIR 1973 SC 1461
- 8 Pandey, J. N., *The Constitution of India* 38 (Central Law Agency, Allahabad, 50th ed., 2017).
- 9 **Universal Declaration of Human Rights, United Nations**, available at: <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights> (last visited on December 19, 2025)
- 10 **International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR)**, available at: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-covenant-economic-social-and-cultural-rights> (last visited on December 23, 2025)
- 11 **Convention on the Rights of the Child, Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR)**, available at: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/convention-rights-child> (last visited on December 22, 2025)
- 12 **African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Banjul Charter), African Union**, available at: <https://au.int/en/treaties/african-charter-human-and-peoples-rights> (last visited on December 30, 2025)
- 13 **Article 25 - Health (Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities), International Disability Alliance**, available at:

- https://www.internationaldisabilityalliance.org/sites/default/files/article_25_crpdpd_1.pdf (last visited on January 05, 2026).
- 14 European Social Charter, Council of Europe, available at: <https://rm.coe.int/168006b642> (last visited on January 10, 2026).
- 15 AIR 1993 SC 2178
- 16 AIR 1995 SC 636
- 17 AIR 1984 SC 802
- 18 1995 (2) SCC 577
- 19 AIR 1992 SC 573
- 20 AIR 2014 SC 1469
- 21 Chaudhary A., Chaudhary B., "Noise pollution: The silent killer of the century" 7 *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health* 2416-2420 (2020).
- 22 European Environment Agency, "Environmental noise in Europe 2025" (2025)
- 23 Coyle K. J., "What Research Says About the Public Health Dangers of Noise Pollution" *Prince William County Department of Conservation and Recreation* (2025)
- 24 Van Kempen E. E. M. M., Kruize H., Boshuizen H. C., Ameling C. B., Willekens L. G. M., de Hollander A. E. M., "The association between noise exposure and blood pressure and ischemic heart disease: A meta-analysis" 4 *Noise & Health* 7-28 (2002).
- 25 Nelson D. I., Nelson R. Y., Concha-Barrientos M., Fingerhut M., "The global burden of occupational noise-induced hearing loss" 48 *American Journal of Industrial Medicine* 446-458 (2005).
- 26 Ganguly P. S., et al., "Occupational noise induced hearing loss in India: Systematic review and meta-analysis" 26 *Indian Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine* 87-94 (2022).
- 27 Balakrishnan S., et al., "Noise pollution and associated hearing loss in a metropolitan city" 15 *Cureus* e39658 (2023).
- 28 Babisch W., "Transportation noise and cardiovascular risk: Updated review and synthesis of epidemiological studies indicate that the evidence for a relationship is stronger than generally assumed" 8 *Noise & Health* 1-29 (2006).
- 29 *Supra* note 24
- 30 *Supra* note 28
- 31 Joopaka A. K., Singh R., Kumar P., "Psychiatric impact of noise pollution in urban areas: A cross-sectional study" 15 *Journal of Community Mental Health Practice* 235-249 (2023).
- 32 Smith J. A., Brown P., Evans L., "Systematic review and meta-analysis of environmental noise exposure and anxiety symptoms in adults" 12 *Environmental Health Reviews* 145-159 (2025).
- 33 Hahad O., Daiber A., et al., "Noise and mental health: Evidence, mechanisms, and public health perspectives" 34 *Journal of Exposure Science & Environmental Epidemiology* 527-545 (2024).
- 34 *Supra* note 28
- 35 D'Souza J., Zhang Y., Xie Z., Fraser A., De Vivo I., Manson J. E., Hart J. E., "Long-term exposures to urban noise and blood pressure in the Nurses' Health Studies" 62 *American Journal of Preventive Medicine* e151-e155 (2021).
- 36 Balamurugan J., Kingsly J., "Physical and cardiovascular implications of noise pollution—A case study at Thoothukudi city" 4 *International Journal of ChemTech Research* 1223-1228 (2012).
- 37 *Supra* note 22
- 38 Janson E., Johannessen A., Holm M., et al., "Insomnia associated with traffic noise and proximity to traffic—a cross-sectional study of the Respiratory Health in Northern Europe III population" 16 *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine* 545-552 (2020).
- 39 Gupta S., et al., "Mental Health Risks from Night time Urban Noise" 354 *Journal of Affective Disorders* 112-120 (2024).
- 40 Basner M., McGuire S., "WHO environmental noise guidelines for the European Region: A systematic review on environmental noise and effects on sleep" 15 *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health Article* 519 (2018).

- 41 Peer M. Y., Mir M. S., Vanapalli K. R., Mohanty B., "Road traffic noise pollution and prevalence of ischemic heart disease: Modelling potential association and abatement strategies in noise-exposed areas" 196 *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 749 (2024).
- 42 Gilani T. A., Mir M. S., Raja Vanapalli K., Mohanty B., "Association of road traffic noise exposure and prevalence of coronary artery disease: A cross-sectional study in North India" 28 *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 53458-53477 (2021).
- 43 Khaiwal R., Shroff A., Mor S., "Non-auditory and auditory impact of daily noise exposure on traffic policemen in Chandigarh, India" *Indian Journal of Public Health* (2025).
- 44 *Supra* note 24
- 45 Vasudevamurthy S., Kumar U. A., "Effect of occupational noise exposure on cognition and suprathreshold auditory skills in normal-hearing individuals" 31 *American Journal of Audiology* 1098-1115 (2022).
- 46 Madan D., Sinha U. K., "Study of academic stress and neuropsychological dysfunction in Indian adolescents with exposure to noise pollution" 13 *The International Journal of Indian Psychology* 5065-5075 (2025).
- 47 Jamir L., Nongkynrih B., Gupta S. K., "Community noise pollution in urban India: Need for public health action" 39 *Indian Journal of Community Medicine* 8-12 (2014).
- 48 Stansfeld S. A., Matheson M. P., "Noise pollution: Non-auditory effects on health" 68 *British Medical Bulletin* 243-257 (2003).
- 49 Wu Y., et al., "Relationship between occupational noise exposure and gestational hypertension in pregnant women in Taizhou City: Cross-sectional study" *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth* (2024).
- 50 Dahabreh D., et al., "Occupational exposure to noise in relation to pregnancy hypertensive disorders and gestational diabetes: A nationwide cohort study" 155 *Environment International* 106688 (2021).
- 51 Gehring U., van Tongeren M., Vermeulen R., Starr M., Fischer P., ten Brink H., Weijers E., Duffus A., Bree L., Brunekreef B., Hoek G., "Impact of noise and air pollution on pregnancy outcomes" 25 *Epidemiology* 409-416 (2014).
- 52 *Supra* note 22
- 53 Miedema H. M. E., Oudshoorn C. G. M., "The sounds of vehicles passing a house: Annoyance and the role of exposure time" 109 *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 1780-1784 (2001).

*** **